

Incidence of BPPV after Mild Head InjuryAkash Geda¹, Suryakant Tiwari², Aastha Solanki³, Mohini Garg⁴¹PG Resident, Department of ENT, GRMC Gwalior, M.P.²Senior Resident, Department of ENT, SRVS Medical College, Shivpuri, M.P.³PG Resident, Department of Surgery, GRMC Gwalior, M.P.⁴PG Resident, Department of ENT, GRMC Gwalior, M.P.

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Abstract:

Background: Benign Paroxysmal Positional Vertigo (BPPV) is a common vestibular condition, characterized by brief episodes of dizziness triggered by specific head movements. While most cases occur spontaneously, head trauma is a well-documented cause of secondary BPPV. This study investigates the incidence and subtype distribution of BPPV among individuals with head injuries.

Methods: A prospective analysis was conducted on 220 patients aged 18 to 65 years (156 males and 64 females) with documented head injuries. BPPV was diagnosed using the Dix-Hallpike and supine roll tests to identify affected semicircular canals. The incidence, gender distribution, and canal involvement were analyzed.

Results: Of the 220 patients, 13 (5.91%) were diagnosed with BPPV following head trauma. The condition was slightly more prevalent in females (6.25%) than in males (5.77%). Among the BPPV cases, the posterior semicircular canal was the most commonly affected (9 cases, 69.23%), followed by the anterior canal (3 cases, 23.08%) and the lateral canal (1 case, 7.69%). Statistical analysis revealed a significant difference between the observed incidence of BPPV in this study and the estimated prevalence of 2% in the general population ($p = 0.00697$).

Conclusion: This study highlights an increased occurrence of BPPV in individuals with head trauma, with an incidence of 5.91% in the study population. The posterior semicircular canal was the most frequently involved, reflecting its anatomical susceptibility to otolith displacement.

Keywords: BPPV, Head Injury, Vestibular Disorders, Posterior Canal, Post-Traumatic Vertigo.

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Introduction

The prevalence of traumatic brain injuries (TBI) is rising in today's world. One of the most frequent aftereffects of traumatic brain injury is dizziness. Vertigo and dizziness are two of the most common symptoms following head trauma [1,2]. The most prevalent vestibular disease following head trauma is benign paroxysmal positional vertigo (BPPV) [3-5]. If otoconia separates from the utricular macula due to the pressures acting on the skull during the trauma, traumatic BPPV (t-BPPV) may result [6]. Additional causes could include microscopic hemorrhages in the membranous labyrinth or otoconia separation from tearing [7].

The pathophysiology of BPPV is explained by two theories: cupulolithiasis (CUP) and canalolithiasis (CAN). The situation where loosened otoconia from the otolith macula bed have been caught in one or more semicircular canals (SCCs) is described by both theories. While CUP refers to the situation where particles stick to the cupula, creating the illusion of movement [8], canalolithiasis defines the condition where there is free-floating otoconia inside the SCC lumen [9,10].

The symptoms of Benign Paroxysmal Positional Vertigo include intense vertigo episodes that last 10 to 20 seconds and are sometimes accompanied by nausea and/or vomiting. The disorder is characterized by brief episodes of vertigo with accompanying nystagmus that are brought on by specific changes in head position with regard to gravity. Benign paroxysmal positional vertigo is diagnosed by positional testing with the Dix-Hallpike (DH) test and/or the supine roll test (SRT). t-BPPV is diagnosed when BPPV is confirmed soon after a well-recorded head trauma. Most studies on t-BPPV apply a time criterion, which may range from a few days up to 3 months. The aim of this study was to estimate the prevalence of t-BPPV after mild head trauma (GCS= 14-15).

Material and Methods

This study is a prospective cross-sectional study. The study population consisted of 220 patients (156 males & 64 females) which include admitted patients of head and neck injury (Motor Vehicle Accident, Blow to the head, Fall from Height, Whiplash injury) in Department of Neurosurgery and

ENT and in the ENT OPD, Gajra Raja Medical College, Gwalior, during a 12-month period from April 2023 to March 2024. The age range was < 80 years. All cases were evaluated and serially followed up to a period of 3 months in the Department of Otorhinolaryngology. In our study, a mild traumatic brain injury patient is a patient with Glasgow coma scale score 14 and 15.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Adult population with TBI (Traumatic Brain Injury) and dizziness and balance problems (Age 12 – 80 years)
2. Mild (GCS 14 or 15 and brief (<5 minutes) loss of consciousness or amnesia)
3. Patients who have accepted to sign consent for the study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Age >80 years and less than 12
2. Moderate (GCS 9–13 and/or loss of consciousness ≥5 minutes or focal neurological deficits)
3. Severe head injury (GCS ≤8)
4. Dizziness or balance problems within the previous 4 weeks before the trauma.
5. Patients who have not accepted to sign the consent form.
6. Patient on mechanical ventilator support.
7. Known oto-vestibular or neurological disorders causing dizziness or balance problems
8. Dementia
9. Substance abuse
10. Seizure disorder

11. Ataxia
12. Anti-epileptic drugs

Diagnostic Procedure

An interview was conducted to begin the diagnostic process, paying close attention to the presence, onset, and symptoms of vertigo or dizziness; the length of attacks; and the relationship between various head movements. Following the interview, a nystagmus evaluation using the Dix-Hallpike and supine roll techniques was conducted. Participant instructions were to remain upright for at least half an hour before to the test. The initial step in the Dix-Hallpike procedure was to lay the subject supine with their neck extended about 20° and their head turned 45° to the side. With the neck bent around 10 to 20 degrees, the supine roll technique was executed by turning the head maximally to one side, then maximally to the other side, and finally back to the first side. Each other participant would take turns tilting their heads to the right and left first in the Dix-Hallpike and supine roll procedures. Each posture was maintained for 20 to 30 seconds if there was no nystagmus. If nystagmus continued, the posture was maintained for about a minute. Patients were followed up at 2, 6 and 12 weeks after the first examination.

Results

A. Incidence of BPPV

Among the 220 patients studied, 13 (5.91%) were diagnosed with BPPV following traumatic brain injury. Of these, 9 were male (5.77%), and 4 were female(6.25%).

Table 1: Demographic Distribution and BPPV Incidence

Parameter	Total (n=220)	BPPV cases (n=13)	Percentage cases
Males	156	9	5.77
Females	64	4	6.25
Overall	220	13	5.91

B. Distribution of BPPV Subtypes

Out of 13 patients with BPPV, 9 had posterior canal type,

3 had anterior canal type and 1 patient had lateral canal type BPPV.

Table 2: Distribution of BPPV Subtypes

BPPV Subtype	Cases	Percentage
Posterior Canal BPPV	9	69.23
Anterior Canal BPPV	3	23.08
Lateral Canal BPPV	1	7.69

Discussion

Vertigo has been defined as the “sensation of motion when no motion is occurring relative to earth’s gravity.” [11] International classification of diseases define vertigo as a feeling of movement, a sensation as if the external world was revolving around the patient (objective vertigo), or as if he himself was revolving in space (subjective vertigo).

In our study, we included 220 patients (156 males and 64 females) of mild head trauma (GCS 14 to 15) over a period of 12 months. Out of 220 patients, 13 patients (5.91%) developed BPPV (9 males and 4 females). Józefowicz-Korczyńska et al. studied 179 patients with mild head injury, where 19 patients were diagnosed with BPPV (10.6%) [4]. Davies et al. studied 100 head injured patients with vestibular complaints, and 15 were diagnosed with BPPV (15%). [12] Balatsouras et al. diagnosed BPPV in 493 patients at a neuro-otology department over a period of 7 years and attributed this to a head trauma in 38 of the patients (7.7%). [13]

Conclusion

This study highlights an increased occurrence of BPPV in individuals with head trauma, with an incidence of 5.91% in the study population. The posterior semicircular canal was the most frequently involved, reflecting its anatomical susceptibility to otolith displacement. Early identification and management of post-traumatic BPPV are essential, as repositioning maneuvers can effectively resolve symptoms. These findings emphasize the need for routine vestibular assessments in head trauma patients to optimize recovery.

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